

4th International Queer Buddhist Conference - IQBC,
October 18 – 20, 2024

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Contents

Preface.....	6
Workshops.....	9
Konen (he, him): The Pure Land is Trans: anyone can become a Buddha: The Meditation of “The 14 Visualizations” taught by Shakyamuni Buddha.....	9
Elias VanDette (they, he): Healing the Inner-Child.....	13
Sibling Yonten (they, them): Contemplating Hope Meditation.....	15
Jampa Wurst aka DJ Jampa Sausage (they, them): Dharma Rap: „Buddhism is Trans“.....	19
Elizabeth (she, her): Heraclitus and the Dharma.....	21
Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Open Forum Peer Support Group.....	23
Stephanie Kolton (she, her):Deep Listening Circle.....	25
Panel: Buddha is Queer.....	27
Talks.....	27
Stephen Kerry (they, them): Michael Dillon also known as Lobzang Jivaka.....	27
Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him): Diverse Identity and Metta of Buddhism.....	29
Panel: Perspectives of the World Towards Transgender/Non-Conforming/Non-Binary People.....	32
Talks.....	32
Ritash (they, them) and Salik Ansari (he, him): Transcending Binaries.....	32
Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Transgender People in History and Culture.....	34
Stevie Inghram (they, she): Honoring The Legacy of Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld: A Buddhist Perspective.....	36
Alexandria Chalfant (she, her) : Searching for Queerness in Premodern European History.....	39
Arts.....	41
Camo aka LA REINA TAINA (she, her): Song.....	41
Noire (she, her): Drawings.....	41
Tashi Choedrup (they, she): Performance.....	41
Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him).....	41
April (her, she): Photography.....	41
Ally: Photography.....	41
Tabitha Mezrah Jennifer Thomson (she, her): Nail Art.....	41
Tatiana Adams (she, her): Poems.....	41
Ryn (they, them): Paintings	41
Rysn (xe, xyr, he, her): film.....	41
Jampa Wurst (they, them): Paintings.....	41
Contributors.....	43
Keynote Speaker: Fresh Lev White (he, him).....	43
Workshop Contributors.....	43
Konen (he, him).....	43
Elias VanDette (they, he)	43
Sibling Yonten (they, them).....	43
Jampa Wurst (they, them).....	44
Elizabeth (she, her).....	44
Stephanie Kolton (she, her).....	44
Panel Contributors	45
Alexandria Chalfant (she, her).....	45
Stephen Kerry (they, them).....	45
Kaushal Ranasinghe (he him).....	45
Ritash (they, them).....	46
Salik Ansari (he, him).....	46

Stephanie Kolton (she, her)	46
Stevie Inghram (they, she)	46
Arts	47
Camó, known artistically as LA REINA TAINA (she, her)	47
Noire LaZard (she, her)	47
Tashi Choedrup (they, she)	47
Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him)	47
April Sun (she, her)	48
Ally	48
Mezrah Tabitha Jennifer Thomson (she, her)	48
Tatiana Adamas (she, her)	48
Ryn (they, them)	48
Jampa Wurst PhD (they, them)	48
Rysn (xe, xyr, he, her)	49
Outlook	51
Acknowledgements	53

Preface

This year, 2024, we already celebrated the 4th International Queer Buddhist Conference with the challenging title „Buddhism is Trans“.

Since I founded IQBC, creating an international, virtual safe space for me and my siblings, queers, queer Buddhists, and mindful or respectful people from all over the globe, intersectional, whether they are atheists, or of different religions, black, indigenous, people of color, people with or without disabilities, and also even supportive allies, this had become an annual event since the 1st International Queer Buddhist Conference in 2021.

In preparation of this conference, I had to face different challenges like hate, bullying, and threatening among social networks, only because of the term „trans“, what could have been understood openmindedly in so many ways like transforming, transgressing, translating, transitioning, transcribing, transmitting, and yes, sure, being transgender. But worldwide it seems that prejudices, and hate against „being woke“ has been increasing.

On the other hand, more than three hundred people were on the registration website. But they seemed to hesitate because of fear to come out of the closet.

So, I got emails and dms etc. telling me, that, the interest and the wish to be part of this conference has been great, but because of fear, people wouldn't register. It would be better in these threatening, dangerous times, to be invisible and silent.

And although we were lucky, that a beautiful keynote speaker agreed to attend, finally we only were a small gathering about forty people. But the 4th IQBC in spite of that was a great success, and people already are looking forward to the 5th IQBC in 2025.

This year it was a great pleasure to have the famous black queer Buddhist teacher, Fresh Lev White on the 4th IQBC. He agreed, although, we only had known us from one virtual event at EBMC, and we have stayed in touch from that event onwards. It felt like a hug, that this powerful, loving transman and Buddhist teacher shared his insight in these difficult times. We were thrilled! He spoke freely, sharing his thoughts, compassion, loving kindness and support to the attendees and other presenters, and also giving a meditation which allowed a peaceful and relaxed beginning of this conference, after all these difficulties.

I was lucky that I was supported again by people, who helped me organizing this conference, like my beautiful webmaster, Melanie, a supportive ally, and yoga teacher, and her partner- Melanie, has been supporting me with my websites, and especially <https://iqbc.org>, from the beginning. Lukas supports me always, when advice with technical difficulties occur.

Also I would like to mention Miriam, my longterm friend from the times we studied at the university. She is also an ally, a Jew, and she has been creating and updating the phenomenal virtual space in gather.town, where you could watch the exhibitions from e.g. Noire LaZard and her amazing development, or films and performances from La Reina Taina, Venerable Tashi Cheodup, Kaushal Ranasinghe, and Rysn.

There you also could find art from Ryn, Tabitha, Dr. Jampa Wurst, and even an ally, and much more. Or you could go on stage for the open mic, if you were courageous enough! ;)

But you also could meet there with old or new friends during the conference for private chats or be there in this beautiful always updated surrounding and meditate, maybe at the fountain, or the river listening to the water and the birds, and many more beautiful spaces, like the Zen garden, boats on the lake or the library, talking about queer or Buddhist books etc.

We had so many beautiful contributors, some I already mentioned. But I would like to mention some more, like Professor Stephen Kerry from Charles Darwin University, Australia, with their talk, who meanwhile have become a supportive friend over continents, or Stephanie Kolton from

Patchwork Transgender Peer Support with talk, workshop and seminar, who also has become a friend, and we are collaborating supporting trans people all over the world. So finally, I had become a facilitator at her organization, called Patchwork (<https://transpatchwork.org>).

Unhappily Venerable Tashi Chodrup had been sick, so that they/she couldn't share their/her talk, but Kaushal Ranasinghe, who is not only a beautiful dancer, but founder of Rainbodhi Europe, shared an exciting talk, I would like to mention Ritash, co-founder of rang.org2020 and their friend Ansari, both from India, and their input, what arts mean for TGNCNB people, especially in difficult times. Also I would like to say thank you to Elias van Dette from the US and his beautiful workshop, mentioning, how important selfcare is for everyone. Due to technical difficulties, a part of the recordings is unhappily missing, and Stevie Inghram had to send their/her talk after the conference. Thank you for recording and sending, Stevie!

And yes, so many, many more presenters, who shared their art, their wisdom, their insight and more on this three days conference. Simply awesome!

Again, it was a big challenge to organize this conference virtually coming together from the West Coast of the US to the East Coast, Europe, Asia and Australia.

These conference proceedings only build an excerpt about the variation or diversity on this 4th IQBC.

We don't record the workshops on the IQBCs due to the safety of the attendees, but we were allowed to record the „Contemplating Hope“ workshop of Sibling Yonten, without Q and A. Sibling Yonten from Plum Village UK is a beautiful supporter or volunteer of the IQBC since the 2nd IQBC, and their warmhearted meditation attracted also people, who do not identify as queer or Buddhist.

But luckily the consent was given for the talks to be recorded as videos, which you can watch on

<https://iqbc.org/recordings-iqbc-2024/>

or on YouTube:

<https://youtube.com/@iqbc570?feature=shared>, where you can give a like, if you want to. Thank you in advance!

After the conference, means – as always - before the conference, because people not only kept asking for the 5th IQBC, but I already am preparing or organizing the 5th IQBC which will take place on Zoom and gather.town from October 31 to November 2, 2025 with keynote speakers Professor Ann Gleig, and Professor Amy Langenberg, USA. Meanwhile, we keep in touch by the monthly Conscious Connections of the IQBC on Zoom as every year, which have their focus on „Arts and Meditation“. They will last until the coming conference as always like a tradition.

Workshops

Konen (he, him): The Pure Land is Trans: anyone can become a Buddha

The Medication of “The 14 Visualizations” taught by Shakyamuni Buddha

Description:

The ancient Buddhist Sutras cannot not only be considered as theoretical texts, but as instructions for practice. The old texts and old translations only need to be adapted to contemporary language and society, as it has been done over many centuries by Buddhist masters across Asia.

In one of the Three Pure Land Sutras, the "Amitayur Buddha Dhyana Sutra" (“The Sutra of Visualization of Immeasurable Life”, jap. Kanmuryôjukyô), the Queen Vaidehi who had been locked up in her palace by her son the crown prince, desperately asks Shakyamuni Buddha for help to escape from her prison and go to the Pure Land of Amida Buddha.

In this Pure Land of Bliss, anyone who thinks of and takes refuge to Amida Buddha will be welcomed, without any restriction or discrimination. According to the 4th of the 48 Bodhisattva vows of Amida Buddha, everyone in the Pure Land has the same form and complexion, so there are no genders, no nationalities or whatsoever, and all inhabitants of this land are totally equal. Once “re-born” into the inclusive and peaceful surrounding of the Pure Land, everyone has the possibility to practice meditation and other practices to become a Buddha.

Responding to the request of Queen Vaidehi, Shakyamuni Buddha then appears before her and teaches her and her 500 attendant women how to attain birth in the Pure Land and become a Buddha by 14 visualizations, starting with the visualization of the Sun.

We will practice these 14 visualizations together in a guided meditation developed by Konen from the “Sutra of Visualization of Immeasurable Life” and the commentary written by the Chinese Pure Land master Shandao (jap. Zendo, 613-681).

The general target for anyone of the meditation is to first clean our hearts and minds from bad actions and experiences in the past, then look into the future with a vision of the Pure Land as an ideal place of equality, love and fairness. Keeping this image in our hearts and minds as a goal to be realized also in our present world if our sangha stands firmly together in unity and equality, this should give us strength and power to withstand any hindrances or obstacles in our daily life.

For Jodo Shu practitioners in specific, this meditation should serve as an auxiliary practice to support their Nenbutsu recitation of “Namu Amida Butsu”.

In the first 15 minutes, there will be an introduction to the history and content of the sutra and its role within Pure Land Buddhism. After that, the guided meditation will start and take about 1 hour. The meditation naturally ends with a short nenbutsu recitation of “Namu Amida Buddha” (“I take refuge to Amida Buddha”) of a few minutes. In the end, there will be some time for questions.

Amida Buddha's Colorful Birds: Music Conveys Values

At the New Year's Concert of the Vienna Philharmonic Orchestra in 2021, conductor Ricardo Muti said to the audience in the orchestra's traditional New Year's greeting before the encore: "Consider culture as one of the main elements in shaping a better society." His words are confirmed in a colorful and imaginative way in one of the three main scriptures of the Jôdo Shû (“Pure Land School” of Japan), the Amida Sutra. It was translated into Chinese by the Chinese monk

Kumârajîva (350-409) and handed down to Japan in this form. In this sutra, Buddha convenes an assembly of 1250 monks, to whom he first describes the "land of supreme bliss" of Amida Buddha as a paradise studded with jewels and gold. In this Buddhaland, "heavenly music is constantly played" (1). Furthermore, there is a "variety of exotic birds in brilliant colors, namely white swans, peacocks, parrots, sârikas (2), kalavinkas (3) and jîvamjîvakas (4). The birds sing six times a day with sounds of harmonious elegance." (5)

But the music of these diverse bird calls not only sounds beautiful, but it also conveys the following virtues and values:

- the "Five Roots of Kindness": trust, effort, mindfulness, mental concentration and wisdom.

They remove obstacles and give motivation to attain enlightenment.

- the "Five Forces", which are reached as the next stage after practicing the Five Roots: the power of faith, which stands in the way of false teachings; the power of effort that keeps the mind and body alert; the power of mindfulness, which prevents wrong thoughts; the power of mental concentration, which prevents distraction; and the power of wisdom that destroys delusions.

- The "Seven Factors of Enlightenment" that provide mental readiness for enlightenment: mindfulness, exploration of phenomena, effort, rapture, calmness, concentration, and equanimity.

- The "Noble Eightfold Path" as a method for attaining enlightenment: righteous views, right intentions, right speech, right actions, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness and right concentration. (6)

The sutra goes on to say, "Amida Buddha created all these birds through transformation so that they would spread the sounds of the Dharma [universal truth] through their songs." (7)

So Amida Buddha teaches the universal principles and methods of becoming a better person through the music of many colorful birds.

The mythological birds mentioned above were depicted in Japanese art, among other things. The Kalavinka bird is depicted in a dance called "karyôbin" of Japanese gagaku music (Chinese court music that came to Japan during the Tang period) in a vermilion costume with colorful feathers. Buddha's teachings are thus conveyed to us through music, dance and painting.

Even more than the sentient beings in the already perfect Pure Land, we in our world need music and culture to remind us of what a better world can look like. The many "colorful birds" of culture in all their diversity deserve our full support, so that they continue to tell the truths of the universe through their art, thus contributing to the formation of a better society. Not only to the Vienna Philharmonic, but to all those who paint, sing, write, dance, write poetry, write poetry, make music, perform, rock out and so on at home or in public.

But regardless of the current situation, every single person is encouraged to continue to be or to become culturally active. Learning poems, songs or pieces of music by heart, acquiring a new language or simply reading books are cultural acts that can be implemented with little effort and can contribute, among other things, to preventing a further brutalization of social interaction with each other.

The Vienna Philharmonic, as well as all musical, artistic and cultural workers who are not discouraged at this time, are to be thanked for their dedication and commitment to give their best despite everything and without spectators present on stage. The sounds of waltzes, polka and other pieces not only put you in a good mood, but also gave you fresh courage for the new year.

The challenge is not to get used to this culturally poor time without concerts, exhibitions, etc., but to try to bridge it as best we can together with "Lebens-Kunst" – "Art of Life". by Kônen, Jan.3, 2021.

Notes:

1. Text: 仏説阿彌陀經 in 「浄土三部経」、浄土宗聖典版、京都
平成二十八年（第二版）：S. 388, Z.3

2. A mythological bird whose name is translated in Chinese as "bird with a hundred tongues" or is interpreted to mean that it also masters human language.

3. A small mythological bird, with a beautiful singing voice, similar to a warbler.

4. A mythological type of falcon or eagle with two heads, also called the "bird of long life".

5. Text: 仏説阿彌陀經 in 「浄土三部經」、浄土宗聖典版、京都
平成二十八年（第二版）：S. 389 Z.4 bis S. 390 Z. 2.

6. Text: 仏説阿彌陀經 in 「浄土三部經」、浄土宗聖典版、京都
平成二十八年（第二版）：S. 390, Z. 2-3.

7. Text: 仏説阿彌陀經 in 「浄土三部經」、浄土宗聖典版、京都
平成二十八年(第二版):S. 391, lines 3-4.

English translation of the Amida Sutra, officially published by the Jodo Shu:

„The Three Pure Land Sûtras. The Principle of Pure Land Buddhism.” Jodo Shu Press, Tokyo 2014:
S. 196ff.

The explanations and substantive notes on the Amida Sutra mentioned in the text above are based
on the footnotes to the English translation of the Jodo Shu (p. 203f.).

Elias VanDette (they, he): Healing The Inner-Child

Description:

Those of us who are LGBTQ+ may be more likely to have gone through trauma. When we occupy the intersections of multiple marginalized identities, the odds can feel stacked against us. For many of us, this wounding began in our early childhood and may even shape our patterns of behavior and belief in the present day. Featuring the research of Dr. Richard C. Schwartz, in this trauma-informed and parts-work inspired workshop, we will discuss the relationship between our inner-critic and our inner-child. We will begin to unpack the patterns of our wounded inner-children that still drive us and discuss ways to begin healing and developing self-compassion. “When we learn to love ALL our parts, we can learn to love all people - and that will contribute to healing the world...” - Dr. Richard C. Schwartz

Sibling Yonten (they, them): Contemplating Hope Meditation

Good morning Dear respected Thay, Dear friends Dear beloved community, welcome to this morning's meditation, I hope that you are able to enjoy the summer, all well as possible.....

Self description

bringing ourselves to a place of stillness both outside & in, practicing our preferred meditation position whatever that may mean for.....

(3xBells)

1: As I breathe in, I recognise the sensation of my in breath. Observing in breath.

As I breathe out, I observe the sensation of my out breath.

Observing out breath, (Bell)

(Half Bell)

2: As I breathe in, I become aware of my body.

Aware of body.

As I breathe out, I am aware of the support that my body offers me.

Supporting body, (Bell)

(Half Bell)

3: As I breathe in, I am hopeful for another in breath.

Hope to breath in.

As I breathe out, I hold gratitude for my out breath.

Gratitude for out breath. (Bell)

(Half Bell)

4: As I breathe in, I recognise my grasping nature.

Recognise grasping.

As I breathe out, I smile to my craving nature.

I smile, (Bell)

(Half Bell)

5: As I breathe in, I recognise my egoic habitual nature.

Egoic nature,

As I breathe out, I know that egoic mind (manas) is not the origin of pure hope.

Not pure hope. (Bell)

Half Bell)

6: As I breathe in, I see the energy of hope is cultivated from the heart.

Hope from heart.

As I breathe out, I understand nurturing hope comes from the heart-mind centre.

Heart centred hope. (Bell)

Half Bell)

7: As I breathe in, I see hope can make the present endurable.

Present endurable.

As I breathe out, I see hope can offer a positive future.

Positive Future. (Bell)

Half Bell)

8: As I breathe in, with hope I witness the opportunity for change.

Possible change.

As I breathe out, I understand the need for hopeful motivation. Half Bell)	Hopeful motivation. (Bell)
9: As I breathe in, I see the impermanence in all things.	Impermanence in all.
As I breathe out, I recognise without impermanence there would be no hope. Half Bell)	Impermanence supporting hope. (Bell)
10: As I breathe in, I welcome the opportunity to bring hope into every mindful breath, step or roll.	Opportunity of hope.
As I breathe out, I welcome the clear motivation that hope offers. TRANSITION PROMPT	Motivation of hope. (Bell)
11: As I breathe in, I enjoy the openness to change that hope offers.	Openness to change.
As I breathe out, I vow to fulfil the diligent, heart-mind practice, that hope needs to flourish. Half Bell)	Flourishing of hope. (Bell)
12: Understanding this is the present moment, I breathe in.	Present moment.
Knowing this is the only moment to enjoy, I breath out.	Only moment, (Bell)

*Mindful movement

*Silent sit

Short reading from Thay's Book: Peaceful Action, Open Heart: Lessons from the Lotus Sutra

“My Dharma is to take up the action of non-action, to practice the practice of non-practice, to attain the attainment of non-attainment. ” This line from the Sutra in Forty-Two Chapters communicates to us that we should not be caught in the outer form, we should not discriminate between non-action and action, being and acting. Many of us try to do many things, yet the more we act the more troubled our family, society, and world become, because the foundation of our being is not yet stable enough. Try practicing the opposite: don't do anything, don't take any action right away, but improve your quality of being through meditation and mindfulness practice. To be in the here and now, fully alive, fully present, is a very positive contribution to any situation. Increasing our insight, compassion, and understanding through the practice of mindfulness is the best thing we can offer to the world. This is the practice of non-practice, the attainment of non-attainment, the action of non-action. We improve the quality of our being so that we have peace and joy, and then we can offer it to our families and communities, and to the world.

Hanh, Thich Nhat. Peaceful Action, Open Heart: Lessons from the Lotus Sutra (pp. 128-129). Parallax Press. Kindle Edition.

Breathe and you know that you are alive.
 Breathe and you know that all is helping you.
 Breathe and you know that you are the world.
 Breathe and you know that the flower is breathing too.
 Breathe for yourself and you breathe for the world.
 Breathe in compassion and breathe out joy.
 Breathe and be one with the air that you breathe.

Breathe and be one with the river that flows.
Breathe and be one with the earth that you tread.
Breathe and be one with the fire that glows.
Breathe and you break the thought of birth and death.
Breathe and you see that impermanence is life.
Breathe for your joy to be steady and calm.
Breathe for your sorrow to flow away.
Breathe to renew every cell in your blood.
Breathe to renew the depths of consciousness.
Breathe and you dwell in the here and now.
Breathe and all you touch is new and real.
- Sister Chan Duc, Breathe, You Are Alive

Jampa Wurst aka DJ Jampa Sausage: Dharma Rap: „Buddhism is Trans“

The Dharma Rap Workshop, invented by Jampa Wurst aka DJ Jampa Sausage as a playful means to speak in rhymes about ethics, politics, society, 2SLGBTQIA+ or queer issues etc. has become a tradition on the conferences. This time we are exploring our gender, whether it's trans, gender nonconforming, non-binary, intersex or whatever, and what that means concerning our relation to the philosophy of Buddhism, s.

<https://www.drwurst.de/dj-jampa-sausage/> and <https://www.drwurst.de/publikationen-raps/>.

Elizabeth (she, her): Heraclitus and the Dharma. Journaling Interactive Workshop

Heraclitus, a classical philosopher, was born in Ephesus and taught in the 500s BCE. He was known for his beliefs in constant change and the unity of opposites. His most famous maxim was "No man ever steps in the same river twice, for it's not the same river and he's not the same man." The Dharma also centers impermanence, that all things change. To consider that Heraclitus taught around the same time as the Buddha raises interesting questions, particularly the idea that there was no monopoly on the understanding and expounding of impermanence.

In this interactive workshop, participants will reflect on the river not remaining the same nor the person. Participants will journal about the following questions:

- How has impermanence impacted your understanding of gender?
- Consider a time in your past and present when you were in the same location, same place, but your experience was different? Describe and explain your experiences.
- How can impermanence be a portal to liberation?

We will begin with a brief reflection on Heraclitus' words and the Buddha's understanding of impermanence and then we will proceed to journaling on one or several of these questions. Finally, participants may share their insights.

One note of importance: Heraclitus' words reflected a period of history of male privilege and his use of "man" for humanity reflects that power dynamic. In our workshop, we recognize and honor all genders.

Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Open Forum Peer Support Group

Mental Health America (MHA) defines a support group as “a gathering of people with common experiences and concerns who meet together to provide emotional and moral support for one another. They encourage a sense of community, a source of empathetic understanding and provide an avenue for establishing social networks.”¹

A support group, at its core, is simply a group of people with something in common coming together to share their lived experiences; the concerns, troubles, conflicts, victories, and questions which affect their mental and emotional wellbeing, their relationships with friends and families, and their interactions with society and culture. Support groups can focus on a specific need or issue, for example discussion on topics related to medical transition, or may be centred on an identity or experience such as that of being a Black non-binary person or a trans person raising children.

In this session, participants will be invited to sit in gender expansive community to share their thoughts, feelings and life experiences, or to hold their silence and quietly reflect on the thoughts and experiences of others, in a safe and accepting environment and in the presence of trans family.

Participants are strongly reminded to refrain from any type of aggressive, abusive, or discriminatory speech or behaviour, to avoid cross-talk, respect each other’s right to speak without interruption, and to follow the guidance of the group facilitator. Participants are also asked to please also be aware of micro-aggressions, as these can be very triggering. Micro-aggressions include statements which convey thoughts or emotions that stigmatise a marginalised group, often by comparison to a generalisation or stereotype.

1. Mental Health America. MHA Mental Health Support Group Facilitator Guide. 2016

Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Deep Listening Circle

In this workshop, participants will experience the open sharing and sense of community that occurs within a circle of like individuals using active listening skills and focusing intently on one topic.

The TNBGNCI deep listening circle is a different kind of peer group. In this space, the group participants discuss one topic or theme brought by the facilitator. The facilitator will discuss the topic in general terms, then ask each participant in turn for their thoughts or comments, feelings or impressions relating to that topic. Participants are encouraged but not required to share. Taking a moment of silence or quiet reflection is also perfectly acceptable. Once all participants in the space have had an opportunity weigh in on the topic, the floor is open to free discussion. Participants are invited to share how others' words and emotions have affected them, questions that arose during the sharing, or concerns they feel having heard all the different thoughts and opinions. Discussion is fluid and more freeform than traditional peer groups, and directed more dynamically by the facilitator.

Unlike more common forms of peer groups in which participants share in turn without comment or interaction, in a deep listening circle crosstalk (or directly responding or answering to the conveyed messages of other participants) is encouraged to foster a free flow of thoughts and ideas. However participants are still asked use "I" statements, speaking only from one's own lived experience, and to refrain from giving advice or speaking in a place of judgement or with disregard for another's lived experience.

In this session, participants are strongly reminded to refrain from any type of aggressive, abusive, or discriminatory speech or behaviour. Participants are also asked to please also be aware of micro-aggressions, as these can be very triggering. Micro-aggressions include statements which convey thoughts or emotions that stigmatise a marginalised group, often by comparison to a generalisation or stereotype.

Panel: Buddha is Queer

Talks

Stephen Kerry (they, them): Michael Dillon also known as Lobzang Jivaka

Michael Dillon is the first transman to undergo phalloplasty and he is also the first westerner to be ordained as a Tibetan Buddhist monk. This paper briefly explores Dillon's life experiences as trans and his time, at the end of his life, where he fled to India to escape the media scandal created by his 'outing' as trans. The focus of this paper will be the often overlooked part of his story where Sangharakshita, an openly-gay English Theravada Buddhist monk and founder of Triratna, actively sabotaged Dillon's desire for full ordination.

Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him): Diverse Identity and Metta of Buddhism

Buddhism, particularly within the Theravada tradition, has often been viewed through a lens that sometimes obscures its inherent inclusivity and compassion. My speech, titled "Diverse Identity and Metta of Buddhism," seeks to illuminate the compassionate and inclusive aspects of Theravada Buddhism, focusing on its treatment of transgender and non-binary individuals seeking ordination.

A central figure in this exploration is Soreiyya Bhikku, a notable transgender individual in Theravada Buddhism, whose story is documented on the Sutta Central website. Soreiyya Bhikku's transformative journey from layperson to monk following a spontaneous gender transition is a powerful testament to the Buddha's metta, or loving-kindness, and his progressive approach to gender inclusivity.

The presentation will delve into the following key areas within the 10-15 minute duration:

1. Historical Context and Inclusivity:

- o Setting the Stage: Understanding the cultural and societal norms during the Buddha's time and how his teachings diverged from these norms to embrace inclusivity.
- o Inclusivity in Early Teachings: Discussing how the Buddha's vision for the Sangha included both monks and nuns, as well as laymen and laywomen.

2. Soreiyya Bhikku's Journey:

- o Transformation and Acceptance: A detailed look at Soreiyya Bhikku's story, highlighting the challenges and acceptance he encountered within the Buddhist community.
- o Canonical References: Exploring the Vinaya Pitaka and other Theravada texts that address gender transition and the ordination of transgender and non-binary individuals.

3. Buddha's Metta:

- o Principle of Metta: Explaining the concept of metta in Buddhism and how it has been applied to foster a diverse and inclusive Sangha.
- o Compassion in Practice: Illustrating the Buddha's compassionate approach towards individuals with different gender identities, including those referred to as "Pandaka."

4. Modern Implications:

- o Contemporary Relevance: How these historical and doctrinal insights can inform modern discussions on gender identity and inclusivity within the Buddhist community.
- o Examples and Case Studies: Presenting additional historical and contemporary examples of inclusivity within Theravada Buddhism.

Conclusion:

- o Affirming Inclusivity: Reiterating that Theravada Buddhism, through its foundational texts and historical practices, has long embodied principles of compassion and inclusivity.
- o Call to Action: Encouraging the modern Buddhist community to embrace these timeless values in today's discourse on diversity and inclusion.

By presenting these elements, the speech will demonstrate that Theravada Buddhism, through its foundational texts and historical practices, has long embodied principles of compassion and inclusivity.

The exploration of Soreiyya Bhikku's story and other similar narratives will underscore Buddhism's enduring commitment to embracing all individuals, regardless of gender identity, in their spiritual journey.

Join us as we uncover the rich history and progressive ethos of Theravada Buddhism, affirming its timeless dedication to metta and its relevance in today's discourse on diversity and inclusion.

Panel: Perspectives of the World Towards Transgender/Non-Conforming/Non-Binary People

Talks

Ritash (they, them) and Salik Ansari (he, him): Transcending Binaries

Heteronormativity and binary gender and sex are considered universal, normal and natural while Gender Sexual and Romantic Minorities (GSRM) is regarded as the exception, abnormal and unnatural. These are incorrect and impossible presumptions, sociobiologically and psychosocially and are rooted in heteropatriarchal majoritarianism and basic insensitivity.

Sexual Orientation Gender Identity and Expression Sex Characteristics (SOGIESC) diversity has been present among Human beings ever since we have been around in the universe although some people may be unaware of or unwilling to believe that. Further, being secretive or selectively disclosing our SOGIESC does not imply that we are heteronormative. Similarly, having gender “typical” socio-cultural behaviour, expression (primarily through names and attire) and physical attributes (voice, facial hair, sex characteristics, et al) does not mean that a person is heteronormative.

With time, experience and better acceptance and awareness of oneself, one may identify differently from what they used to earlier. It is not necessary that one may be able to fit within the confines of certain identities. Questioning, exploring or uncertainty is a part of this journey and there may well be folks who are unsure of who they are or what they identify as. Sometimes it may be easier to say what one is not rather than what one is.

Ground realities

However, many people (including some binary GSRM persons) want you to fit into binaries for their own comfort and convenience. Consequently, one often lives with the burden of explaining oneself or finding a place in a binary world. The binaries are not just limited to gender and sexuality but include those of faith and no-faith, decision and indecision and action and inaction. Lack of acceptance by family, society, religious traditions and legal systems brings queer people to constantly tussle between two binaries with all sides expecting a definite response. Suppression of gender and sexual diversity by anyone is usually an uncomfortable choice and sometimes a compulsion based on impacting socio-cultural attitudes and experiences (bias, rejection, discrimination, exclusion, ostracisation and violence). In fact, Identities are a continuum and can be dynamic. Everybody is on a unique journey of self-discovery that is shaped by their environment, circumstances and certain innate factors.

As GSRM community peer counsellors with intersecting socio-cultural identities, we have faced questions on how our GSRM community members can be “more gay” or “trans enough” or “less queer” to survive comfortably. Lately, such questions are arising mainly from queer persons who consider themselves to be gender non-binary and/or sexually fluid. These questions arise because, within and outside the GSRM community, non-binary queers sometimes find only minimal understanding and acceptance of their SOGIESC.

This paper will demonstrate how self-acceptance, peer support and creative expression can help queer persons overcome some of the above issues, to some extent. Of course, we may still choose or have to live with dichotomies and dilemmas within and among us and beyond.

Stephanie Kolton (she, her): Transgender People in History and Culture

The transgender, Non-Binary, Gender Non-Conforming, and Intersex (TNBGNCI) community has existed since the dawn of time. In this seminar, participant will be introduced to TNBGNCI contributions to culture and society from the earliest written records 5000 years ago to the modern day. From the ancient temples of Sumer and Akkad to the nations Africa, from the battlefields and courts Europe to the plains, forests, and jungles the Americas, and from the cities of Asia to the waters of Pacifica, gender expansive peoples have existed throughout history as religious leaders, warriors, performers, judges, leaders, and teachers. Transgender culture has influence law, music, and dance. Transgender people have won battles, informed ethics, and resolved disputes. The richness, depth, and breadth of TNBGNCI history informs the the development of societies and and gives a road-map of the evolution of the species.

At the end of this seminar, participants will be understand the role and impact of transgender community on culture, religion, philosophy, and the arts. Participants will learn how gender diversity has added to the sum of human existence and enriched the lives of millions. As well, participants will be able to intelligently speak on transgender history and the importance of protecting TNBGNCI people and culture globally.

Stevie Inghram (they, she): Honoring The Legacy of Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld: A Buddhist Perspective

Description:

In this talk, Stevie Inghram will reflect on the harrowing work of Queer Physician, Humanitarian, and Sexologist Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld who founded both the Scientific Humanitarian Committee and The Institute of Sexual Research of which organized their energies and focus on advocating for queer and transgender rights in both the 19th & 20th centuries.

Throughout his legacy, Dr. Hirschfeld's work seamlessly aligned with many tenets of the Buddhist path including compassion, loving-kindness, non-judgment, and advocacy for the most marginalized and oppressed in society. Ultimately, his belief in the natural diversity and expansivity of human gender and sexuality led him to encourage acceptance of all beings just as they are. Join Stevie in celebration of this queer visionary, Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld!

By Stevie Jiyo Inghram, M.S, YT, AWC, Future Naturopathic Physician (NMD)

Honoring The Legacy of Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld: A Buddhist Perspective

To conclude LGBTQIA+ history month (October), I wanted to take a moment to honor the legacy of one of our most prolific LGBTQIA+ scholars & activists, Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld. In his time, Hirschfeld was a visionary gay Jewish Physician and activist often called the "Einstein of sex". His work fundamentally laid the foundation for modern LGBTQIA+ advocacy. Born in Prussia in 1868, Hirschfeld's commitment to understanding and supporting the diverse expressions of human gender and sexuality exemplifies the Buddhist principles of compassion (*karuṇā*), wisdom (*prajñā*), and loving-kindness (*metta*). Even though he likely did not practice Buddhism specifically, he exemplifies the living embodiment of a Bodhisattva given his dedication to relieving the suffering of those most marginalized in society at the time.

Hirschfeld's groundbreaking work began with his advocacy for homosexual rights. In 1896, he published *Sappho and Socrates*, a pamphlet that openly defended same-sex love which was quite a revolutionary stance in an era when homosexuality was criminalized globally. As a Physician, Hirschfeld had a strong conviction that same-sex attraction was a natural part of human diversity; this exemplifies the Buddha's teachings on acceptance of one's true nature. Ultimately, through Hirschfeld's scientific writings, lecturing, and advocacy he promoted understanding and harm reduction which aimed to dismantle prejudices that fueled societal suffering. These actions show his commitment to *right speech* through laying the groundwork for challenging laws and norms that stigmatized and marginalized LGBTQIA+ people.

In 1897, Hirschfeld took a historic step by founding the Scientific-Humanitarian Committee, one of the world's first LGBTQIA+ rights organizations. This committee aimed to repeal Paragraph 175, the German law criminalizing male homosexuality. The committee's motto, "Justice Through Science," aligns closely with the Buddhist belief that the generation and embodiment of wisdom can lead to the alleviation of human suffering. In Buddhism, *prajñā*, wisdom or discernment, is vital to living a compassionate life and fighting against injustice. Hirschfeld's belief that scientific understanding could transform social attitudes reflects this notion of *prajñā* which in this context aimed to reveal the lived realities of those within gender & sexually expansive (GSE) communities. In doing so, he sought to alleviate the suffering caused by ignorance, prejudice, and misinformation. Although his committee's efforts were ultimately unsuccessful in repealing Paragraph 175, this officially marked the beginning of the organized LGBTQIA+ rights movement that laid the foundation for our ongoing efforts in attaining legal rights and sovereignty for *all* queer and trans people globally.

Beyond solely focusing on homosexual advocacy, Hirschfeld also expanded his research to the transgender community. At that time, he coined the term *transvestite* to describe those who identified and presented as a gender different from the one assigned at birth. While this term has

evolved and is rarely used in the 21st Century, Hirschfeld's early work resonates with the Buddhist teaching of *anattā*, or non-self, which suggests that human identity is not bound by a singular or rigid identity and is often fluid and dynamic throughout the human lifespan while simultaneously acknowledging one's deeper essence or true nature. In this ultimate sense, Hirschfeld strongly championed the idea that human gender and sexuality is simply a part of the natural order of the universe.

In 1919, all of Hirschfeld's vision as a Physician had coalesced when he established the Institute for Sexual Science/Research in Berlin which was the first of its kind. This institute was a center for gender & sexually affirming healthcare, counseling, and education on LGBTQIA+ issues which aligns with the Buddhist principle of *right livelihood*; a call for the work that we do in our daily lives to promote well-being and the reduction of suffering among all beings. The Institution for Sexual Science/Research provided medical care and support for LGBTQIA+ individuals and became a place of refuge where queer and trans people of that time could find others that offered compassion and acceptance, especially important in a society that largely rejected them leading to further isolation and discrimination.

One of Dr. Hirschfeld's most pioneering contributions was his medical support for transgender individuals. At the Institute, he offered early forms of hormone treatments and surgical procedures to support gender transition. Hirschfeld's work with individuals like Dora Richter, one of the first people to undergo gender-affirming surgery reflects a deep respect and reverence for each individual's journey toward self-realization and the recognition of aligning one's outward presentation with their inward sense of self.

Despite his massive contributions to the queer & trans community, Hirschfeld faced significant opposition from conservatives and fascist groups. His progressive views and advocacy made him a target of hostility, and in 1933, the Nazi regime targeted his Institute by raiding his facilities and forcefully removing and burning thousands of books and research materials on human sexuality and gender identity. This tragic event underscores the Buddhist concept of *dukkha*, unsatisfactoriness or suffering, which often arises from attachment to rigid beliefs, intolerance, and not seeing things as they truly are, known as *yatha-bhutam darshanam*. In response to this hardship, Hirschfeld demonstrated extreme resilience, an attribute highly valued in Buddhism; despite all of the fear and intimidation he faced in Nazi, Germany, he continued to advocate for LGBTQIA+ rights. This level of determination and unwavering commitment to social justice in the face of immense adversity reflects his fervor in standing for the greater good of queer and transgender people across the world. Sadly, much of his work was lost through the destruction of his institute and the many documents contained within which reveals the ever pressing reality of impermanence as acknowledged by the Buddha himself. Despite the loss of much of his life's work, the spirit of his advocacy and clinical care has endured throughout this last century. Ultimately, from a Buddhist perspective, true contributions to society transcend material forms and live on through the wisdom, compassion, and action they inspire in others; echoing the lasting impact of Hirschfeld's work. May Dr. Magnus Hirschfeld's advocacy and care continue to reverberate in our ongoing struggle for queer and trans liberation globally. May it be so!

Alexandria Chalfant (she, her): Searching for Queerness in Premodern European History

This talk will explore some of the pitfalls and potential avenues for research into queerness in Late Antiquity, the European Middle Ages, and Early Modern Europe. Particular attention will be given to pre-reformation English religious life and the Lives of the Saints.

Arts:

Camo aka LA REINA TAINA (she, her):

She released her new song „Toca Corazón“ on the 4th IQBC and shared a video of „Love“ by Nat King Cole on our virtual space created for the conference on gather.town.

Noire LaZard (she, her):

She shared her amazing drawings, a development one can follow through the last years on the conferences on gather.town.

Tashi Choedrup (they, she):

Tashi-la shared a video of a Christmas song and dance, they sang, on gather.town.

Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him):

Kaushal shared videos of the awesome dance performances on gather.town.

April Sun (her, she):

April shared her meditative photography on gather.town.

Ally:

Delighted that IQBC is also supported by allies. One was so kind to share a photo on gather.town they made.

Tabitha (she, her):

She shared her exciting nail art on gather.town.

Tatiana Adams (she, her):

Tatiana writes poems, which she shared in written form on gather.town.

Ryn (they, them):

Ryn shared her paintings of animals full of phantasy on gather.town.

Rysn (xe, xyr, he, her):

Rysn shared a film xe had made on gather.town about doing rap with others.

Jampa Wurst (they, them):

Jampa shared some of their paintings, s. also <https://atelier.drwurst.de>

Contributors

Keynote Speaker: Fresh Lev White (he, him)

Fresh “Lev” White is a love and compassion activist. He offers mindfulness, mediation, and diversity trainings as tools for shifting towards more authentic, conscious, and passionate living. He teaches and writes about how unconditional love and self-compassion are the ultimate gateways to honoring and understanding others, thus healing our communities and our planet.

Fresh “Lev” White

Diversity Trainer, Speaker, Mindfulness Teacher & Minister of Love

Learn more about my offerings here:affirmativeacts.org

You can book a free consultation with me here:booktimewithlev.as.me

Workshop Contributors

Konen (he, him)

Konen (he, him) holds a diploma in Japanese Language and Translation and has been ordained as a Buddhist monk of the Pure Land tradition of Honen Shonin in Tokyo in 2019. After studying Japanese language from 1993 to 2000 in Bonn and Tokyo, he has been working for Japanese companies and finished a training as Shiatsu practitioner. He aims to serve all beings in finding their natural way of life towards their personal “Pure Land” and come to peace of heart and mind with themselves and with others, guided by the Great Compassion of Amida Buddha.

“Birth in the Pure Land is possible without exception.” (Honen Shonin)

More information at www.jodobuddhismus.org.

Elias VanDette (they, he)

I am a Certified Peer Specialist in the state of New York. Part of what I love about being a peer specialist is being able to lead with my lived experience. I may not be a clinician with a masters, but I have walked the road of recovery I attempt to lead others on. I understand first hand what it is like to struggle with mental health and what it takes to regain your footing after a crisis. Much of the work I do in the realm of mental health revolves around working with people after a major crisis or relapse and helping them to gain the skills needed to take their power back. My approach to mental health is always trauma-informed and resilience centered. My work with the LGBT+ community is very near to my heart as a transgender / non-binary person myself. This unique perspective shapes a more nuanced understanding of how systems of oppression can have a very real impact on mental health and access to mental health care.

Sibling Yonten Phuntsok (they, them)

Sib. Yonten (they/them) is a self-ordained Buddhist monastic (2017) who’s root traditions are in the Tibetan Kagyu lineage (2008). Though from 2014 has been following teachings of Ven. Thich Nhat Hanh & the Plum Village tradition. Their walking of the Buddha’s path started in 1999 when they attended 3-day Lojong teachings in London, offered by HH the 14th Dalai Lama. They is a Neuro-Diverse & disabled person, a military veteran & part of the 2SLGBTQIA+ community also is the representative for PVUK’s newly forming ‘Inclusion circle for Disability and Neurodiversity’.

Jampa Wurst (they, them)

Dr. Jampa Wurst (PhD) studied comparative religion at Freie Universität Berlin, where they earned their PhD in 1999. In their studies, they conducted field work among Tibetan Buddhist nunneries in exile India. They was ordained twice with white robes in Theravada Buddhism. From 1991 – 1999 they studied at the Tibetan Centre in Hamburg the “7 Years Systematic Studies of Buddhism”. They finished with a certificate and earned a small yellow hat of the Gelug tradition, so similar to a teacher/acharya.

Furthermore, they is a lifelong member of <https://sakyadhita.org>, has held regular workshops about LGBTQQIA+ at Buddhist Conferences.

As DJ Jampa Sausage, they invented <https://medium.com/@jampawurst/dharma-rap-ac5d94a231e9>, a playful medium to stir interest in education, research, Buddhist, ethics, feminism, diversity, and politics.

On the artistic side, Jampa is not only a rapper but also a painter with more than 100 paintings in their <https://atelier.drwurst.de/en/>. Realizing the need for a safe space for queer Buddhists, having been bullied in their Buddhist communities, they founded the International Queer Buddhist Conferences shortly before the pandemic. Since 2021 the IQBCs have become an annual event.

Elizabeth (she, her)

„Autobiographical statements are awkward for me. There are the checklist items: mother, teacher, devotee of Bodhisattva Tara, and practitioner of TM. But the core of my practice is a need for the peace that only spirituality brings. It is like a merchant travelling the Silk Roads. There is the promise of success if the journey is finished and a bit of pleasure awaits at the end of the road but in the meantime, there are deserts to survive and crevasses in mountains not to fall in. And then even at the end of the journey, there are more journeys until the final journey. Like that merchant, I need something to hold onto. I need Bodhisattva. I need meditation. I need a spiritual life. The fearless and the foolish may not but I know the perils of the journey. I need Bodhisattva.”

Stephanie Kolton (she, her)

Stephanie Joy Kolton (she/her) is the Founder and Executive Director of Patchwork Transgender Peer Support. A former emergency medical first responder working primarily in socio-economically disadvantaged urban communities, disaster response with a focus on uncivil and austere environments, and international relief and aid work in the global south, Stephanie brings her nearly 20 years of critical crisis intervention and calm, de-escalating demeanour to serve the TNBGNCI community with her characteristic gentility and humour.

In her years facilitating peer support groups, Stephanie witnessed the struggles many of her community members faced in accessing regular support and care, particularly in more underserved parts of the country and among those with unmet intersectional needs. Stephanie recognised the urgent need for free access to peer support as a necessary tool for the health and wellbeing of the transgender community.

In 2022, she began facilitating a small group of gender-expansive people in a deep listening circle. She saw how with every discussion, each member grew stronger and more confident in themselves, and how that confidence allowed them to lead healthier, more fulfilling lives. She knew she had to do more. So in 2023, she created Patchwork, to bring vital peer support to every transgender, non-binary, gender non-conforming, and intersex person in the country.

Patchwork Transgender Peer Support, a non-profit organisation, is dedicated to promoting the health and wellness of transgender, non-binary, gender non-conforming, and intersex people through engagement, support, and community. Patchwork believes freely available access to peer

support and gender-related resources is one of the cornerstones of personal and emotional growth, and is key to achieving social and health equity for all gender expansive peoples.

Website: transpatchwork.org

Instagram: [@transpatchwork](https://www.instagram.com/transpatchwork)

Threads: [@transpatchwork](https://www.threads.net/@transpatchwork)

Panel Contributors

Alexandria Chalfant (she, her)

Alexandria Chalfant was a Dornsife Doctoral Fellow in History and a PhD Candidate in Medieval History at the University of Southern California in the 2010s before leaving academia to pursue social work. She received her Master's in Social Work from Fordham University in 2024. She lives in New York's Hudson Valley with her dog, Ollie.

Stephen Kerry (they, them)

Dr Stephen Kerry (they/them) is a lecturer in sociology at Charles Darwin University, Australia. They are a genderqueer, non-binary second-generation Australian of British migrant parents and was first in their family to attend university. Dr Kerry is a Zen Buddhist, volunteers as a telephone crisis supporter, and they live in Melbourne, Australia with their two cats. For over twenty years, Dr Kerry's research has focused on the lived experiences of Australians who live on sex and gender margins of society. In 2005, they completed their PhD, which documented the lived experiences of Australians with a variation of sex characteristics (sometimes called 'intersex') which was published in 2009 under the title: *Are You a Boy or a Girl?* In 2018, Dr Kerry published *Trans Dilemmas* which was a study of the health needs of trans and non-binary people living in the Northern Territory. This research is the first academic work that documents the lives of trans and non-binary First Nations Australians, also known as sistergirls and brotherboys. In 2019, Dr Kerry started investigating the lives of LGBTQIA+ Buddhist Australians. Preliminary results of this research has presented at the 1st and 3rd International Queer Buddhist Conference.

Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him)

Kaushal Ranasinghe is a dedicated Buddhist practitioner and advocate for gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights. Born and raised in Sri Lanka, Kaushal has faced personal challenges due to their queer identity within a predominantly conservative Buddhist community. With a background in journalism and creative writing, Kaushal has contributed numerous articles to Sri Lankan newspapers, magazines, and online platforms. Their advocacy is further supported by a postgraduate degree in gender and health from the University of Colombo, and extensive experience in delivering lectures on gender issues, often contextualized within Buddhist teachings.

Kaushal is the co-founder of Rainbodhi France and practices dhamma with Tilorien Monastery in Belgium. They are also a law advocate with a graduate degree in law (LLB) from New Buckinghamshire University. Currently, Kaushal is pursuing studies at the Walpola Rahula Foundation, deepening their understanding of early Buddhist texts. Their commitment to inclusivity is reflected in this book, which aims to make Buddhist teachings more accessible and relevant to marginalized communities. Through "Inclusive Dharma: Embracing Diversity in Buddhism," Kaushal seeks to create a safe and welcoming space for all practitioners, championing the Buddha's message of compassion and inclusivity.

Ritash (they/them)

Ritash is an India based agnostic neuroqueer gender fluid Ace, writer, DEIB consultant, LGBTQIAP+ peer counsellor and co-founder, RANG Foundation (a pan-India collective of and for intersectional queers). They enjoy penning verse, mentoring youth and camera tricks.

Insta: [@ritashachanta](#)

PayPal: apushpa@gmail.com

Salik Ansari (he/him)

Salik Ansari is an early career professional primarily interested in ethics.

Stephanie Kolton (she, her)

Stephanie Joy Kolton (she/her) is the Founder and Executive Director of Patchwork Transgender Peer Support. A former emergency medical first responder working primarily in socio-economically disadvantaged urban communities, disaster response with a focus on uncivil and austere environments, and international relief and aid work in the global south, Stephanie brings her nearly 20 years of critical crisis intervention and calm, de-escalating demeanour to serve the TNBGNCI community with her characteristic gentility and humour.

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Website: transpatchwork.org

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Threads: [@transpatchwork](#)

Stevie Inghram (they, she)

Stevie Inghram (They/She) is a U.S. based queer & trans femme who is a passionate advocate for the gender & sexually expansive (GSE) community. Throughout Stevie's global advocacy in the spheres of human rights, public health, and holistic medicine, they have interwoven their decades of practice in Yogic & Buddhist philosophy which has compelled them to advocate for the most marginalized among us.

With this enthusiasm, Stevie hosts Queer Story Time, The Podcast which serves as a brave space for sharing queer & trans stories of radical affirmation, acceptance, empowerment, and healing; QST is available on all major podcasting platforms and on YouTube. Beyond Stevie's podcasting and advocacy, she works one-on-one with queer & trans people as a Yoga & Ayurvedic Therapist and will

soon be graduating as a Naturopathic Physician in June 2025. You can find them on social media @queertransthiving

Arts

CÁMO, known artistically as LA REINA TAÍNA (she, her),

is an Afro-Latina Trans artist whose music and spiritual activism embody the essence of “Buddhism is Trans” the title of the coming 4th IQBC in the Fall of this year.

Her work integrates Latin House, Dembow, and electronica with Buddhist teachings of compassion and interconnectedness. Through her art, she challenges societal norms and fosters radical inclusivity, emphasizing the transformative power of spiritual and creative expression. Her performances are a testament to the resilience and joy of Trans identities, promoting healing and unity within the queer Buddhist community. You can check out her work on her website at www.lareinataina.com.

Support Black Trans* Researchers!

Noire La Zard (she, her)

Brandi “Noire” La Zard (she, her) was raised in Houston, Texas. La Zard received her BFA (Individualized Film/Video/Performance and Drawing) from California College of the Arts in San Francisco/Oakland. Her work has been selected and featured in the Creative Quarterly, as one of the national finalists in the Fine Art Professional category for the No. 27 circulation. She’s also featured in WMN Zine publication dedicated to artists living with disabilities. Ms. La Zard exhibited work in the group exhibition Bombay Sapphire Artisan Series – Regional – Houston Museum of African American Culture, Houston, Texas. La Zard currently lives and works in Houston, Texas: „My work explores my life-long curiosity and fascination with form. Specifically, typography and architecture have directly influenced my artistic approach, aesthetic. The forms are created through free association; in addition, predetermined forms are used as the catalyst to develop the overall composition. My studies in graphic design, typography, architecture, abstract constructivism, and pop art have shaped my aesthetic, thus far, in the majority of works to date. Merging gestural mark-making with structured line-drawing dominates the overall composition. In this realm of competing styles of mark-making (gestural, precision mark-making), the works highlight the desire to create freedom, harmony, and balance between those worlds.“

Tashi Choedup (they/she)

Tashi-la is a trans-feminine Buddhist monastic (nunk) based out of Hyderabad, India. Tashi is a founding member of Telangana Hijra Intersex Transgender Samiti, and Queer Swabhimana Yatra. They closely work with queer-trans communities and with local social justice movements. They are part of Queer-Trans Wellness and Support Center (QT Center), Yugantar, Hyderabad which provides services such as a 24/7 helpline, drop-in space, free mental health services, free legal aid, and crisis intervention support among others to LGBTQIA+ folks.

Kaushal Ranasinghe (he, him)

Kaushal Ranasinghe is a dedicated Buddhist practitioner and advocate for gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights. Born and raised in Sri Lanka, Kaushal has faced personal challenges due to their queer identity within a predominantly conservative Buddhist community. With a background in journalism and creative writing, Kaushal has contributed numerous articles to Sri Lankan newspapers, magazines, and online platforms. Their advocacy is further supported by a postgraduate degree in gender and health from the University of Colombo, and extensive experience in delivering

lectures on gender issues, often contextualized within Buddhist teachings.

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April Sun (her, she)

April Sun (her, she) is a retired Transwoman that resides on the central coast of California.

"I can say I am inspired by the photos I take. As I live through my journey I feel the images I capture tell a story, a story the viewer can create. What does a visual snapshot in time mean to you? What do you feel, what does an image say to you? You get to create your own story. Photography to me is an expression of my way of living."

Ally

No bio.

Mezrah Tabitha Jennifer Thompson (she, her)

"Hello, I'm new to just about everything in this journey of self-discovery and identity, outside of running through all the fantasies, simulations, thoughts, ideas, and etcetera in my mind. I'm trying to be more social, expand my social circle, and meet new people. Feel free to contact me via ["oxofintieoxo@gmail.com"](mailto:oxofintieoxo@gmail.com).

Tatiana Adams (she, her)

Hello everyone my name is Tatiana my pronouns is she/her/hers. And I'm calling from NYC 22 years of age and my favorite thing to do is to write poems and read poetry because of how poetry can symbolize so many things and it could lead to see universal message.

Ryn (they, them)

My name is Ryn, I'm from MA in the US. I'm Queer Nonbinary/Agender. I use They/Them pronouns. I've been drawing/painting all of my life. It brings peace and happiness. I tend to draw furry critters, but I also draw arachnids as they are a special interest of mine. Hope you enjoy!

Jampa Wurst PhD aka DJ Jampa Sausage (they, them)

Dr. Jampa Wurst studied comparative religion at Freie Universität Berlin, where they earned their PhD in 1999. In their studies, they conducted field work among Tibetan Buddhist nunneries in exile India. They was ordained twice with white robes in Theravada Buddhism. From 1991 – 1999 they studied at the Tibetan Centre in Hamburg the "7 Years Systematic Studies of Buddhism". They finished with a certificate and earned a small yellow hat of the Gelug tradition, so similar to a teacher/acharya.

Furthermore, they is a lifelong member of Sakyadhita, has held regular workshops about LGBTQIA+ at Buddhist Conferences.

As DJ Jampa Sausage, they invented Dharma Rap, a playful medium to stir interest in education, research, Buddhist, ethics, feminism, diversity, and politics.

On the artistic side, Jampa is not only a rapper but also a painter with more than 100 paintings in their digital atelier. Now, it is her pleasure to organize the International Queer Buddhist Conference.

Rysn (xe, xyr, he, her)

No bio.

Outlook

Meanwhile, since I founded the International Queer Buddhist Conferences, IQBCs, as a safe space for queer or 2SLGBTQIA+ people, who are Buddhist or mindful and respectful, this has become an annual event. The IQBCs are open not only for Buddhists or 2SLGBTQIA+ people, but also for every religion or philosophy, also if people are atheists, and allies of the queer community, an intersectional global community.

The monthly Conscious Connections of the IQBC also have become a regular event with the focus on arts and meditation.

The need for safe spaces like the annual IQBCs and their Conscious Connections are still needed, especially in these times that are politically changing to rightwing views full of prejudice, hate and threatenings against marginalized communities.

So, this means that after the conference is before the conference!

We stay in touch monthly, but also on social media or email to support each other, also by facilitating peer groups. So for example IQBC.org and Patchwork (transpatchwork.org) are collaborating in this way.

Already, I am organizing the 5th IQBC, which will take place from October 31 to November 2, 2025, with the title „Buddhism – Human Rights – Queer Rights – vs. Abuse“ with keynote speakers Prof Ann Gleig and Prof Amy Langenberg. I am very happy to share this wonderful news with you!

So, if you have an idea for a contribution, feel free to write to me or info@iqbc.org!

Again the 5th IQBC will provide the global queer Buddhist and mindful family with scholarly talks, workshops, and especially artsy expressions because artsy expressions make it possible for queer and Buddhist people to survive and to live in spite of difficulties by expressing themselves, their gender, their diversity, their facets among this global rainbow community. The International Queer Buddhist Conferences will be a safe space for this as long as there is this need.

On <https://iqbc.org> you always will be updated.

As I mentioned on the previous Conference Proceedings:

„May it become a tradition of further International Queer Buddhist Conferences – IQBCs - as a safe and protected place, no matter, which sexuality, gender, color or culture etc. you belong!

May all beings be happy.

May all beings be safe, and well.

May all beings be peaceful and at ease.“

Acknowledgements

I am very grateful for my global team, who encouraged me to organize the 4th International Queer Buddhist Conference with the for many challenging title „Buddhist is Trans“.

Thank you very much to Miriam, my longterm friend, ally, and creator of the beautiful virtual space on gather.town. To discuss things with her and listen to her insight is a big support.

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I am grateful for the support of Br. Yonten and their current support answering emails concerning questions about the helplines we provide on <https://iqbc.org> and supporting me, like Miriam, Noire, and Kaushal as co-hosts, so that everyone on the conference could feel safe.

Already I am organizing the 5th IQBC, which will take place from October 31 to November 2, 2025, with the title „Buddhism – Human Rights – Queer Rights – vs. Abuse“ with keynote speakers Prof Ann Gleig and Prof Amy Langenberg, who kindly agreed. Thank you!

So, if you have an idea for a contribution, feel free to write to me or info@iqbc.org!

